

KOREAN CUISINE GONE GLOBAL

Papers from Shorenstein APARC's
Korea Program Conference

December 2024

Edited by Dafna Zur

Stanford

Walter H. Shorenstein
Asia-Pacific Research Center
Freeman Spogli Institute

Korean Cuisine Gone Global

KOREAN CUISINE GONE GLOBAL

**Papers from Shorenstein APARC's
Korea Program Conference**

December 2024

Edited by Dafna Zur

The Walter H. Shorenstein Asia-Pacific Research Center (Shorenstein APARC) addresses critical issues affecting the countries of Asia, their regional and global affairs, and U.S.-Asia relations. As Stanford University's hub for the interdisciplinary study of contemporary Asia, we produce policy-relevant research, provide education and training to students, scholars, and practitioners, and strengthen dialogue and cooperation between counterparts in the Asia-Pacific and the United States.

Shorenstein Asia-Pacific Research Center
616 Jane Stanford Way E301
Stanford, CA 94305-6055
650.723.9741 | aparc.fsi.stanford.edu

CITING THIS PUBLICATION: Zur, Dafna, ed. 2024. "Korean Cuisine Gone Global: Papers from the Shorenstein Asia-Pacific Research Center Conference." Shorenstein Asia-Pacific Research Center working paper. Stanford University, December.

COVER: Close-up of naengmyeon (Sammyvision/Getty Images).

These papers were written for the April 2024 Korea Program conference “Korean Cuisine Gone Global.” The conference was made possible in part by the Korea Foundation and the Friends of Shorenstein APARC.

Contents

	Contributors	ix
I.	From Food to Cuisine	1
	Korean Diasporas and the Globalization of the <i>Papsang</i> <i>Dafna Zur</i>	
II.	Transnational Tastemakers in the Seoul Food Scene	7
	Korean Adoptees and the Language of Food <i>Rebecca Jo Kinney</i>	
III.	Actually, Mother Really Didn't Like Jjajangmyeon	19
	The Desire of Noodles in the Diaspora <i>Robert Ji-Song Ku</i>	
IV.	The Stickiness of Zainichi Korean Food Routes	
	Food Memoir as Affective Archive <i>Jooyeon Rhee</i>	31

Contributors

Rebecca Jo Kinney is an interdisciplinary teacher and scholar of American Studies and Ethnic Studies, and an associate professor at the School of Cultural Studies at Bowling Green State University. Kinney's award-winning first book, *Beautiful Wasteland: The Rise of Detroit as America's Postindustrial Frontier* (University of Minnesota Press, 2016), argues that contemporary stories told about Detroit's potential for rise enable the erasure of white supremacist systems. Her research has appeared in *American Quarterly*, *Food, Culture & Society*, *Verge: Studies in Global Asia*, *Radical History Review*, and *Race&Class*, among other journals. Her second book, *Mapping AsiaTown Cleveland: Race and Redevelopment in the Rust Belt*, is forthcoming from Temple University Press in 2025. She is working on a third book, *Making Home in Korea: The Transnational Lives of Adult Korean Adoptees*, based on research undertaken while a Fulbright Scholar in South Korea.

Robert Ji-Song Ku is an associate professor of Asian and Asian American Studies at Binghamton University (SUNY) and the managing editor of *Foundations and Futures: Asian American and Pacific Islander Multimedia Textbook* of the Asian American Studies Center at UCLA. His teaching and research interests include Asian American studies, food studies, and transnational and diasporic Korean popular culture. Prior to Binghamton,

he taught at Cal Poly, San Luis Obispo, and Hunter College (CUNY). He is the author of *Dubious Gastronomy: Eating Asian in the USA* (University of Hawai'i Press, 2014) and co-editor of *Eating More Asian America: A Food Studies Reader* (NYU Press, forthcoming 2025), the sequel to *Eating Asian America* (NYU Press, 2013). He is also co-editor of *Pop Empires: Transnational and Diasporic Flows of India and Korea* (University of Hawai'i Press, 2019) and *Future Yet to Come: Sociotechnical Imaginaries in Modern Korea* (University of Hawai'i Press, 2021), as well as the Food in Asia and the Pacific series for the University of Hawai'i Press. Born in Korea, he grew up in Hawai'i and currently lives in Culver City, California.

Jooyeon Rhee is an associate professor of Asian Studies and Comparative Literature and director of the Penn State Institute for Korean Studies. She specializes in modern Korean literature and culture. Her main research concerns Korean popular literature, with particular emphasis on transnational literary exchanges and interactions. Currently, she is writing her second book on cultural imaginations of crime and deviance manifested in late colonial Korean detective fiction. Her other research interests include diasporic art and literature and food studies.

Dafna Zur is an associate professor of Korean literature and culture in the Department of East Asian Languages and Cultures and director of the Center for East Asian Studies at Stanford. Her first book, *Figuring Korean Futures: Children's Literature in Modern Korea* (2017), interrogates the contradictory political visions made possible by children's literature in colonial and postcolonial Korea. Her second project explores sound, science, and space in the children's literature of North and South Korea. She has published articles on North Korean popular science and science fiction, translations in North Korean literature, the Korean War in children's literature, childhood in cinema, children's poetry and music, and popular culture. Zur's translations of Korean fiction have appeared in wordwithoutborders.org, *Modern Korean Fiction: An Anthology*, and the *Asia Literary Review*.

From Food to Cuisine

Korean Diasporas and
the Globalization of the *Papsang*

DAFNA ZUR, STANFORD UNIVERSITY

In 2024, at the time of the publication of these papers and in the wake of Stanford’s celebratory event, “Korean Cuisine Gone Global,” the following statements seem self-evident: Korean ingredients such as *doenjang* and *gochujang* have become as ubiquitous as, say, oyster sauce and miso paste; kimchi has joined the list of trendy, sought-after fermented miracle foods (like kombucha and kefir) that tout multiple health benefits; Korean restaurants—both low- and high-end—are easier to find than ever; and there is seemingly no end to the number of Korean cooking shows that viewers worldwide can stream on multiple online platforms.

These three statements capture the successful move that Korean food has made from niche to mainstream and from “food” to “cuisine.” For over twenty years, academic scholarship and media have attested to this evolution. Journalists have covered the country’s export policies that directly affect the globalization of Korean cuisine¹ (Park 2024); they have pointed to the registration of some key ingredients with the Codex Alimentarius Commission² as a measure of success (Friedman 2024); and they have noted the increased number of Korean restaurants glob-

¹ For example, in February 2024 the South Korean Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs announced a plan to increase the number of Korean restaurants abroad, substantially scale up the restaurant sector, and increase the number of Michelin-rated Korean restaurants.

² “The Codex Alimentarius is a collection of internationally adopted food standards and related texts presented in a uniform manner. These food standards and related texts aim at protecting consumers’ health and ensuring fair practices in the food trade” (FAO n.d.).

ally. In addition to these top-down efforts, the connection between the increased visibility of Korean food and the Korean Wave has not escaped attention. *Hallyu* is the “Korean wave” that crashed on the shores of Asia in the late 1990s and has been delivering Korean popular culture content to the rest of the world ever since. Interest in K-pop and K-dramas has led to exponential growth of interest in other areas of Korean culture, including cuisine. This is the theory, at least, and it helps to explain the shift in perception of Korean food to some extent.

This narrative, however, misses something important. By drawing a direct line between gastro-diplomatic policies, campaigns, and lobbying efforts in institutions like the Codex Alimentarius and UNESCO and the rise in popularity of Korean food, it is easy to lose sight of the fact that food creation and consumption is a highly sensorial, personal experience, born of mobility and experimentation, with a trajectory that may not follow the dictates of policies or campaigns. In their introduction to the *Verge* issue dedicated to the food of global Asias, Ray, Rhee, and Chen (2023, vi) turn their attention to the way that cuisine in Asia has always been created by “transnational flows; border making and breaking; culinary heritages and innovations; and the relationship between the production, distribution, and consumption of food *in Asia and its multiple diasporas*” (my emphasis). What this means is that the globalization of Asian food has always been, to quote the authors again, a “messy process” with multiple directions, and a process in which Asian diasporas have played a significant role (ix), above and beyond, to cite Robert Ku (2014, 5–6), the geographic locales and “political imaginings of Asia.” The three contributors to these working papers draw attention to just that: the overlooked ways in which diasporic communities have often had to contend with, and even resist, hegemonic narratives of authenticity and origins. In the process, different diasporic actors—many of whom have taken leading roles in the culinary world not of their own volition—have made significant contributions to what later, and ironically, has been dubbed as authentic and original.³ About the search for authenticity in food, Ku (2014, 4) has written: “To believe in authenticity is to rely on transcendental means to answer questions posed by a reality deemed untidy and undesirable.” The illusion that

3 See Rhee’s account of Kim Yangnŭng and other Zainichi women and the reasons they turn to the kitchen and Kinney’s accounts of Pierre, James, and Mister B.

“authenticity” can be grasped, captured, and marketed from above or disseminated from below is one that the three authors seek to challenge.

Before pointing to highlights from the three papers, it is important to draw attention to affective elements that are a critical part of scholarship on food. To reiterate a point I stated earlier, food is a matter not only of the head and eyes, but also of the heart and gut. In other words, any study of globalization that seeks to explain Korean food’s successful crossing of borders must take into account what Highmore (2013, 102) and others have termed *gastropoetics*: “a form of aesthetic attention that allows . . . varied regions to be glimpsed in the entanglements of an ordinary act of cooking.” Food is central to what Highmore and others have called “theaters of the flesh and of the psyche”—in other words, an appreciation of food needs to take into account who prepares it and where, the context in which it is eaten, and the way it engages the senses and leaves an imprint on individuals, families, and communities. Critically, the eating experience cannot be limited, or reduced to, one that is affiliated solely with a national territory. The three papers speak to this point. Highmore’s suggestion, that a study of food requires an approach of “critical regionalism,” is key here: he challenges us to “think about the overlapping forms of territory that are articulated and inhabited by cultural practices like cooking and eating” (108). Understanding Korean cuisine, I contend, requires an openness to the diverse ways that Korean food has come to be shaped by the local *and* the global, by its multiple stakeholders and constituents both inside and outside the Korean Peninsula.

All of this is to say that transnational flows of food cannot solely be explained by the evocation of government investments or even the triumphant success of *Hallyu*, as tempting as it may be. Personal histories, like the ones explored by Jooyeon Rhee, Rebecca Jo Kinney, and Robert Ku, reveal the ways that migrant actors—whose movement has been a critical part of Korea’s turbulent twentieth century—have navigated national borders on the one hand and contended with gatekeepers of authenticity on the other. Rhee, Kinney, and Ku demonstrate the critical roles played by less-than-glamorous participants in the process of producing, distributing, and eating. It is these actors that have moved ingredients, flavors, and dishes across time and space, sharing them with diverse communities and enabling the elevation of the Korean table, the *papsang*, from food to cuisine.

The three papers below connect Korean food with broader questions of individual and national identity, family and community, the food of the home and the food of the heart. They challenge us to think about what Rebecca Kinney has called in her scholarship “food ways.” Kinney (2023, 132) refers to food ways as those that “highlight the interconnected relationships to food born through dislocation, isolation, adaptation, and (possible) reunion with and from natal foodways.” In her case, personal histories of adoptee Koreans who return to Korea to “eat back” or “feed back” (recalling the postcolonial classic, *The Empire Writes Back*, by Ashcroft, Griffiths, and Tiffin) their multiple communities. For Kinney’s informants, Food becomes a Way—toward an authentic home, rich with complexity and contradiction.

The movement of food is also at the center of Rhee’s paper. She examines a 2019 memoir by a prominent member of the Zainichi community. In its focus on art and food, this memoir effectively captures what Rhee calls the “sticky” positionality of the Korean community in Japan, particularly how it continues to navigate tensions between Japan, South Korea, and North Korea. Strikingly, Rhee points out that while the memoir writer expressed a yearning for a “return” to a united homeland, the author’s lifework became about establishing a company whose motto, “Food is Art,” reflects his desire to feed his community as it is, not as he wishes it to be.

Finally, Robert Ku takes us on a journey that begins with a K-pop classic, g.o.d’s song “To Mother” from 1999, which enacts the drama of a grown son who looks back on Korea’s era of poverty and his mother’s sacrifices, symbolized by the way she turns down a delicious bowl of noodles so that her son can eat it all himself. Ku asks the age-old question that is begged every time one enters a Chinese-style Korean restaurant — *jjajang* or *jjampong*? Noodles in black bean sauce or in spicy broth?—to show how his personal history illustrates the intricate relations of China and Korea, Shandong and Incheon, Incheon and Honolulu, and how an iconic dish can trigger contradictory feelings, for different reasons, in members of the same family.

The three papers provide a sense of how Korean food is both the result of and the impetus for global circulation. Robert Ku reminds us of how Korean food results from global circulation, as in the case of Chinese migrants from Shandong who brought *jjajang* to Korea. At the same time,

Korean food provides the impetus for global circulation: Koreans in Japan or Korean adoptees in the United States create opportunities for new food ways and become food ways themselves. The scholars reveal what can only be shown through personal histories and through inquiry into the “theater of the body and the psyche”: that eating, preparing, and sharing food is a process that implicates multiple positions. While we celebrate Korean food for its diversity, creativity, and remarkable achievements over the last twenty years, we also wish to point to the ways that Korean cuisine—like all cuisines—is dynamic, versatile, the result of the passion of many, and an endlessly fascinating subject of study.

References

- Ashcroft, Bill, Gareth Griffiths, and Helen Tiffin. 2002. *The Empire Writes Back : Theory and Practice in Post-Colonial Literatures*. 2nd ed. Routledge.
- Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO). n.d. "About Codex Alimentarius." <https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/en/>.
- Friedman, Sarah. 2024. "The \$40m Bet that Made South Korea a Food and Cultural Power." *The Hustle*. April 5, 2024. <https://thehustle.co/originals/the-40m-bet-that-made-south-korea-a-food-and-cultural-power>.
- Highmore, Ben. 2013. "Migrant Cuisine, Critical Regionalism and Gastro-poetics." *Cultural Studies Review* 19 (1): 99–116.
- Kinney, Rebecca Jo. 2023. "Flavors of East LA in the Heart of Seoul: Transnational Korean Adoptee Food Ways." *Verge: Studies in Global Asias* 9 (2): 130–156. doi:10.1353/vrg.2023.a903025.
- Ku, Robert. 2014. *Dubious Gastronomy: The Cultural Politics of Eating Asian in the USA*. University of Hawai'i Press.
- Mishan, Ligaya. 2022. "When a Country's Cuisine Becomes a Cultural Export." *New York Times*. October 12.
- Park, Hye Ri. 2024. "Strategy to Raise Food Industry's Value to KRW 300B by 2027." *Korea.net*. February 5.
- Ray, Krishnendu, Jooyeon Rhee, and Tina Chen. 2023. "Cooking Cultures: Global Asias on the Move and in the Making." *Verge: Studies in Global Asias* 9 (2): vi–xviii. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1353/vrg.2023.a903018>.
- Rhee, Jooyeon. 2019. "Gender Politics in Food Escape: Korean Masculinity in TV Cooking Shows in South Korea." *Journal of Popular Film and Television* 47 (1): 56–64. doi:10.1080/01956051.2019.1563445.

Transnational Tastemakers in the Seoul Food Scene

Korean Adoptees and the Language of Food

REBECCA JO KINNEY, BOWLING GREEN STATE UNIVERSITY

A classic French quiche and financiers for takeout in a first-floor storefront in Yeonnam; a bottle of wine and light appetizers shared among friends in a second-floor street-view space in Hoegi; a weekend pop-up brunch with a DJ spinning '80s and '90s hip-hop and R&B in a whisky bar in Eulji-ro. . .

These are but three snapshots of Seoul's food scene in the early 2020s. And, as I will present here, they are a way into the provocation of "Korean Cuisine Gone Global," the conference for which this paper was written.

These three very different dining and drinking experiences in a city filled with food and drink were created by three people who were born in Korea, transnationally adopted to the United States and France, and in their twenties return migrated to Korea, where each of them has lived for over a decade.

In deciding to focus my paper on the experiences of these three specific tastemakers in the Seoul dining scene, I am also highlighting the experiences of a particular subset of the Korean diaspora: three of the two hundred thousand people who were transnationally adopted from Korea during seventy-plus years of ongoing Korean adoption.¹ And, as you will see from the stories I share today, these three tastemakers are

¹ Among international adoption programs, South Korea's is the largest, oldest, and longest running in the world. Pertinent to this paper, the United States is the largest market for children from Korea, accounting for approximately two-thirds of these nearly two hundred thousand placements over the last sixty-five years (McKee 2016, 137). France is the second-largest adoption

in collaboration with other members of the Korean diaspora, Koreans, and other foreigners that are living in Seoul, which begs the question of which I do not have a singular answer: What makes Korean food *Korean*?

Obviously, the foodways of Korea, the rich and long history of Royal Cuisine, fermentation, and temple food are undeniably registered as “Korean Food.” These historic foodways are practiced and continue to be studied and shared today.² Yet, historic foodways are continually undergoing adaption, and everyday eating practices are continually changed through global flows of people into and out of Korea, most famously encompassed by the dish known as army base stew (*budae jjigae*).³ Is Korean food that is carried, adapted, and changed still *Korean*?

I think of this often when remembering Ji-Yeon Yuh’s recounting of a Korean military bride who, when she arrived in America, was so hungry for the tastes of home that she made *gochujang* from stale bread, soy sauce, and crushed red pepper. This makeshift gochujang was a prized commodity to give and receive, as only a few had “mastered” making this crude semblance. The maker presented her creation to the new arrival, who turned her nose at it and re-gifted this culinary mashup being passed off as a staple flavor. However, a few weeks later, this no longer new arrival unsuccessfully attempted to retrieve her cast-off; the recipient would not return the imposter gochujang because by then, as everyone knew, this was the closest approximation one could get to the flavors of Korea (Yuh 2002, 132–3).

This moment that I recount here seems improbable as gochujang now appears in every Asian market across the globe and is even featured in such foods as Shake Shack burgers or atop a turkey burger at a self-proclaimed “local American hangout” in a suburban Detroit strip mall (Shake Shack 2021; Beau’s Grillery 2024).⁴ And it is the leap between Ji Yeon Yuh’s story of the imposter gochujang and “What is Gochujang

market, although much smaller than the United States, with 11,165 official adoptions between 1968 and 2008 (Kim 2010, 21).

2 See for example, the “The Institute of Royal Cuisine,” accessed April 16, 2024, <http://www.food.co.kr/food/board.php?board=home> and the “Korean Temple Food Center,” accessed April 16, 2024, <https://www.koreatemplefood.com/eng/agency/ex.html>.

3 See for example Kinney 2023, 135 for a brief literature review on budae jjigae and Baik 2020, Cho 2014, Ku 2014, and *Korea Herald* 2012 for more extended variations on the histories of this dish.

4 During the conference, as I sat next to Robert Ji-Song Ku, I wanted to ask if he ever imagined that Korean *jangs*, and their fermented funkiness, often labeled as some of the most dubious

and How to Use It” (Riske 2023), a 2023 *Better Homes & Gardens* article, which seems improbable to me, a Korean adoptee⁵ who grew up in the Midwest in the 1980s and 1990s. I could never in my wildest imagination think that *Better Homes & Gardens*, a century-old institution of aspirational American homemaking, would run a story on Korean red pepper paste. My, how times have changed!

What makes Korean food *Korean*? Foodies, chefs, critics, and food scholars who love to debate “authenticity” often regard “fusion food” with disdain and proclaim to be experts in what is and is not real, myself included. So I wonder today, as a way into this paper about three diasporic tastemakers, if you will hold with me this question:

Is this Korean food?

- Instant noodles (*k’öpnamyön*) slurped at the counter of a 24-hour convenience store in the middle of the night?
- The same *k’öpnamyön* slurped over a desk in Ohio while watching K-drama?
- An abalone “taco” nestled in a yuba shell?⁶
- Red beans over shaved ice (*p’at’binsu*) eaten at a Tous Les Jours in metro Detroit?
- My favorite pizza in the world: smoked chicken and ham with a spicy barbeque tomato sauce topped with macaroni and cheese. . . served at a pizza place in Seoul?

Is this Korean food? Korean food gone global, indeed.

of all flavors and smells, would appear (albeit watered down) atop burgers served up in chains and restaurants across the globe. See Ku 2014, 190–223.

5 Throughout this essay, I use the term adoptee for clarity of language and style rather than the critical adoption language of a “person who was adopted” (Pak 2020). Additionally, adoptee is the common terminology used by and in the large and diverse community of people who have been adopted. However, I want to point to the continuing conversations about language and critical adoption language occurring among the community of people who were adopted (Pak 2020). The usage of adoptee often serves to infantilize (i.e., adoptees as perpetual children) and also suggests that the person’s primary identity is surrounded and framed through adoption.

6 The dish, one of Chef Sung Anh’s signature opening bites at Mosu, Korea’s only three-star Michelin restaurant, is a play on the Tijuana street tacos he ate as a teenager growing up in San Diego (Yan 2022).

Transnational Adoptee Food Ways

People sometimes ask what makes adopted returnees different from other diasporic Koreans who return to Korea; are their experiences not similar?⁷ There are overlaps common to people of the Korean diaspora—a return that feels both familiar and awkward, a sense of continuing placelessness in “homeland” and also in country of citizenship, varying fluency in language, culture, and family ties. But, by virtue of the context of migration for the majority of people who were transnationally adopted, there are distinct differences.

The three tastemakers I introduce below, Pierre, James, and Mister B,⁸ bring a particular relationship to food born of a unique diasporic experience. By highlighting a portion of their stories, I further develop the idea of “transnational Korean adoptee food ways” (Kinney 2023, 131–32). The break of the compound word “foodways” into “food” and “ways” is an intentional gesture wherein this space represents a break of culture, family, and connection to natal Korean foodways that, for transnational adoptees, was in nearly all cases sudden and immediate, and more often than not experienced in isolation. Additionally, this split allows the space for new “ways” of experiencing Korean food culture to emerge.

Pierre, James, and Mister B’s experiences come from a larger research study I conducted from July 2021 to April 2022. I interviewed forty-two people who had been transnationally adopted as infants and children and subsequently return migrated as adults to live in Korea (Kinney 2022). While the research was not explicitly focused on food, many respondents spoke about their experiences and relationships with food (Korean and otherwise) as a part of home. The three I focus on here have a distinct connection to the food industry through their work. Specifically, I suggest that their experiences building careers around food in the country of their birth illustrate how food can operate as community, language, and process for transnationally adopted people.

7 On Asian American return, see Wang 2021, Lee 2018, Yamashiro 2017, Tsuda 2016, and Kibria 2002.

8 These are all pseudonyms self-selected by the participants.

Food as Community

I met Pierre on an afternoon in early December at the wine bar he and his girlfriend co-own down the street from Kyung Hee University. The second-floor space in a curved street-facing building was bedecked in festive Christmas trim, the sunlight streaming through the windows and bathing the room in warm light. Hours before service began, the bar was quiet enough to faintly hear traffic from the street. Pierre was born in Korea in the early 1980s and adopted to a small town near Bordeaux, France. At the time of our interview, he had been living in Korea for thirteen years, during which he had worked in various industries: military, tourism, and then hospitality.

While the interviews were primarily about home and community, we spent a fair amount of time speaking about his wine bar as reflective of the communities he and his girlfriend are part of. Pierre said, “The wine bar we built is representing what we are, me and my girlfriend.”⁹ Their clientele—one-third Korean, one-third Russian-speaking, and one-third Western (including French, other Europeans, Americans, and Canadians)—reflects their community. Both proprietors identify as diasporic Koreans and run an establishment that regularly hosts speakers of Korean, Russian, French, and English.¹⁰ On any given evening, the room is abuzz with laughter, the clinking of glasses, and a mixture of these four linguistic patterns in every possible configuration and accent.

While some considered it a “French wine bar,” this space was obviously more than that. It defied simple classification because of the sheer number of cultural influences that shaped the menu, the atmosphere, and the culture of the bar itself. Pierre reflected on this when he shared the different ways he and his partner interacted with their patrons, both friends and customers.

It’s interesting because, for example, Russian clients, when they come, they always, it’s a politeness that as an owner, as host, you should come

⁹ Interview with “Pierre,” December 5, 2021

¹⁰ Relevant to this discussion is Pierre’s girlfriend’s identification as Koryōin (ethnic Koreans living in the former Soviet Union). Her grandparents migrated to Russia during Japanese colonization and were subsequently forced to migrate to Central Asia, where she grew up. She was raised in a community of diasporic Koreans who spoke both Russian and a local language. She has lived in Seoul for several years.

and share. They will offer you drinks from their bottles, and you need to stay with them and talk to them, and everything. You take French. French do not share their bottle with you. And if you go to sit with them, they're really happy, but they're not going to share the bottles unless you're a really close friend, and everything, but most of the time, it doesn't happen. And Koreans, if you even come to see them, it's weird. So, even friends, you don't sit with them. The French stay really long, they drink a lot, but they stay really long. Russians, they stay really long, but they drink more than Koreans and French, and they do things kind of quickly more like the Korean style. And then Koreans, they either come really long and drink nothing or they drink a lot, but they stay a really short time. There's no in-between.¹¹

We laughed as he relayed this, half in jest and half in all seriousness. These three cultural groups, all with distinctive and rich drinking cultures described here in humorous shorthand, coexist in this one space, this one bar in Seoul. The proprietors move fluidly and fluently between these cultural groups, hosting, adapting, and creating a distinctly global and local Seoul community.

The Language of Food

I met James in a café in the shadow of Yongsan, a short walk from where he lives in Gyeongnidan, both part of the larger Itaewon neighborhood. At the time of our meeting, James had recently transitioned out of a position as head of menu development for a Korean brewery. He was running a few pop-up projects with a Korean American friend and business partner. He was in the midst of some playful experimentation as he considered his next venture. James is in his mid-thirties, was born in Korea, and adopted as an infant to the United States. He grew up in a rural community on the West Coast, then moved to the Bay Area for college and stayed there until moving to Korea in his mid-twenties. He reflected, "A big thing for me in the Bay Area was language. There I was doing poetry, I was teaching, I was facilitating."¹²

11 Interview with "Pierre," December 5, 2021.

12 Interview with "James," February 9, 2022.

James recalls a huge shift in connection around language after he moved. “I came to Korea and I couldn’t do any of those things really. Except for teaching. And so food became this way that I sort of connected with people. . . . It was the way that we could all sit in a room and not really have any shared language, but I could cook something for them and they’d be like, ‘Wow, this is really crazy, and good and fun.’ So we could have an experience together.”¹³

Throughout our conversation, James repeatedly turned over the idea of “Korean food” as deeply linked to community and what it means to be home in a place. James enjoys eating and cooking Korean food and is knowledgeable about the cuisine. He told me,

I think with food you always have those, everyone, I think has those core foundational experiences with food that generally happen when you’re younger, that positive or negative, shape your relationship with food and what you crave and what makes you feel like home. Right? And for me, that will never be Korean food.¹⁴

Yet, his menus are deeply engaged with the local context and its Korean and global influences. He reflected,

For example, what we’re doing with our pop-ups right now, I think there’s a way in which we can approach Korean food and think about it under the lens of people who are third culture or diasporic and say something that hopefully adds to the scene, not just an understanding of what Korean food can be, but also what it even means for something to be Korean food.¹⁵

Near the end of our conversation about food, language, and home I asked James, “And in the language of food then, what is home to you?” He replied,

I think personally, it’s less about the product and it’s more just about the experience of gathering. I think professionally, for me, it’s cooking something that creates room for myself to be not just myself, but the adoptee diaspora to be understood differently in terms of their relationship with Korea. . . . But the gatekeeping in terms of what is Korean and what isn’t

13 Interview with “James,” February 9, 2022.

14 Interview with “James,” February 9, 2022.

15 Interview with “James,” February 9, 2022.

is really strong. I guess part of our hope and motivation for our pop-ups, which do have Korean elements in them, is like, “Hey, these are the things that we find enjoyable and that we nerd out about with Korean cuisine, and even though you may feel us as other or outside, I think what we’re doing here, is, given that culture is always changing and shifting, what we’re doing here is part of that change and shift. And I think an important one”. . . . Food for me, it’s always connected to, it’s the lens, for which I see society, and community, and relationships.¹⁶

Although James did not come to Korea to pursue a career in the culinary world, he has built a solid reputation through his hard work and years of on-the-job training, working his way from cooking as a hobby through experiences washing dishes to working as a prep/sous chef, and then finally moving up through a growing brewery concept to head of menu development. After over ten years in Korea, he had, in the months before our meeting, decided to settle permanently in Seoul. As he considers his next move, he holds food and the connections and community it enables as key to making a home for himself.

Food as Process

I met Mister B on his day off in the test kitchen of the bakery where he works in Yeonnam-dong. We drank coffee and snacked on the remnants of a recipe test for a Japanese-style Basque cheesecake he was developing. Mister B, who was in his early forties, was adopted as a toddler to French Brittany and had been living in Seoul for almost ten years. Before returning to Korea in his early thirties, he had a successful career in Paris making visual effects for the global film industry. He came to Korea to study Korean and, as he describes it, to “process my emotions and the way I interact with people,” particularly around his experiences with racism growing up as an Asian man in France.¹⁷

Mister B now lives in Seoul, among both other adoptees and what some in this community sometimes refer to as “Korean-Koreans” (Park Nelson 2016, 104). He has found a sense of peace in Korea that did not have while living in France. When he first moved to Seoul, he lived for

¹⁶ Interview with “James,” February 9, 2022.

¹⁷ Interview with “Mister B,” November 14, 2021.

a while in the KoRoot guesthouse, a first stop for many in the adoptee community.¹⁸ It was there he met an American Korean adoptee he eventually started dating, and they married. In 2016 he and his then-wife moved to Perpignan in the Catalan region in the very south of France to study pastry. Mister B shared, “We planned to live several years in France, like just five years, something like that. And work in some pastry shops. But. . . my ex-wife didn’t like it, it was very rough time.” They stayed only two years, first for training and then internships in Perpignan and then taking a second internship in Nantes, in the Loire Valley. Mister B’s now ex-wife quit the second internship on the second day of their six-month contract and returned early to Seoul. Mister B remained in France, completing this second internship; he returned to Seoul, started working in pastry shops, and ended their marriage.

The training in classical French pastry was rigorous and challenging, as expected: long hours, lots of yelling, and little pay. Mister B said, “[We had] no money, you know, we were interns. So no money. . . . It wasn’t enjoyable at all. Plus the racism.” As Mister B elaborated on their experiences, it became clear that it was the constant racism, both in the kitchen and on the streets, that wore the couple down. Mister B, referencing times when they walked to and from work, said, “In the streets, there are some people just staring, you know?” At home, he said, “Even there, we open the window and they look inside,” and the people on the streets would shout into their home. “Not many times, just a few times. But I think it was hard for her, it surprised her. Me, I wasn’t surprised, I knew already [*chuckle*].” While he and his wife both grew up in primarily white families in white communities in France and the United States, respectively, and were no strangers to racial microaggressions and acts of racism, their experience as pastry interns in the South of France was unparalleled and created a continued state of psychological distress for them.

For Mister B, the training and knowledge he gained formally as a *pâtissier* in France has been a strong foundation for his work in pastry shops in Seoul. And, in all likelihood, his native fluency with French culinary culture is valued by his Korean employers as they seek to make

¹⁸ KoRoot closed its guesthouse in 2023. It has appeared in many adoptee narratives. See, for example, Kim 2010 and Wills 2021.

not Korean French pastry¹⁹ but rather “classic” French pastry in Seoul. But, as evidenced by his test recipe for Japanese-style Basque cheese-cake, what is French pastry in the heart of Seoul? Moreover, why is this demarcation important?

What makes Korean food *Korean* food?

I seek to illustrate with these three brief snapshots the dynamic, ever-changing, and indefinable relationships we have with food. By focusing on the “food ways” of three tastemakers in the early 2020s Seoul food scene, diasporic Koreans—born in Korea but raised in France and the United States, and whose work in Seoul contributes to the flavor and vibes of this global city—I aim to show how culture is born of an ongoing dialogue between and among the local and the global.

Although these three particular conversations traversed at least four distinct languages and cultures, there was not a word that could sufficiently capture the cultural complexities of food, foodways, and all that is wrapped up in the consumption, preparation, tradition, and innovation of food, not to mention the feeling, emotion, and symbolic heft that food serves. It is so much more than simply calories, which is why ideas of “authenticity” and “fusion” are insufficient yet often serve as the simplest ways to transmit the process of food adaptations and changing foodways. While none of these observations are new—anthropologists, food studies scholars, and critics have long discussed foodways and culture—by situating the experiences of a distinct sub-group, transnationally adopted Koreans, we can access different ways of understanding food and food ways that diverge and converge in Seoul, a persistently local and unquestionably global city.

19 The long love affair with Korean-style French-inspired pastries, most famously represented by the brands *Tous les Jours* and *Paris Baguette*, goes all the way back to 1988 (Shah 2015).

References

- Baik, Crystal Mun-hye. 2020. *Reencounters: On the Korean War and Diasporic Memory Critique*. Temple University Press.
- Beau's Grillery. 2024. "Menu." Last accessed April 17. <https://www.beaus-bloomfield.com/menu>.
- Cho, Grace M. 2014. "Eating Military Base Stew." *Contexts* 13 (3): 38–43.
- Kibria, Nazli. 2002. "Of Blood, Belonging, and Homeland Trips: Transnationalism and Identity Among Second-Generation Chinese and Korean Americans." In *The Changing Face of Home: The Transnational Lives of the Second Generation*, edited by Peggy Levitt and Mary C. Waters. Russell Sage Foundation.
- Kim, Eleana. 2010. *Adopted Territory: Transnational Korean Adoptees and the Politics of Belonging*. Duke University Press.
- Kinney, Rebecca Jo. 2022. "Adult Korean Adoptees Making Home and Building Community in South Korea." Unpublished Fulbright Scholar research.
- . 2023. "Flavors of East LA in the Heart of Seoul: Transnational Korean Adoptee Food Ways." *Verge: Studies in Global Asia* 9 (2): 130–56.
- Korea Herald*. 2012. "Uijeongbu Restaurant Owners Take Pride in 'Army Base' Stew." June 26. <http://www.koreaherald.com/view.php?ud=20120626000729>.
- Ku, Robert Ji-Song. 2014. *Dubious Gastronomy: The Cultural Politics of East-Asian in the USA*. University of Hawai'i Press.
- Lee, Helene K. 2018. *Between Foreign and Family: Return Migration and Identity Construction among Korean Americans and Korean Chinese*. Rutgers University Press.
- McKee, Kimberly D. 2016. "Monetary Flows and the Movements of Children: The Transnational Adoption Industrial Complex." *Journal of Korean Studies* 21 (1): 137–78.
- Pak, Kris. 2020. "Critical Adoption Language." *SPEAK: Solidarity and Political Engagement of Adoptees in Korea* (blog). March 1. <https://adoptees-speak.wordpress.com/2020/03/01/critical-adoption-language/>.
- Park Nelson, Kim. 2016. *Invisible Asians: Korean American Adoptees, Asian American Experiences, and Racial Exceptionalism*. Rutgers University Press.
- Riske, Heather. 2023. "What is Gochujang?" *Better Homes & Gardens*. February 28. <https://www.bhg.com/what-is-gochujang-7112501>.
- Shah, Khushbu. 2015. "Pastries Born in France, Raised in South Korea: How Two South Korean Bakery Chains Popularized Treats Combining Eastern Flavors and Western Techniques."

- Eater. December 30. <https://www.eater.com/2015/12/30/10685588/korean-bakery-paris-baguette-tous-les-jours>.
- Shake Shack. 2021. "It's Here! Shake Shack's New Korean-Inspired Menu." September 17. <https://shakeshack.com/blog/our-food/its-here-shake-shacks-new-korean-inspired-menu>.
- Tsuda, Takeyuki. 2016. *Japanese American Ethnicity: In Search of Heritage and Homeland Across Generations*. New York University Press.
- Wang, Leslie Kim. 2021. *Chasing the American Dream in China: Chinese Americans in the Ancestral Homeland*. Rutgers University Press.
- Wills, Jenny Heijun. 2021. *Older Sister. Not Necessarily Related*. McClelland & Stewart.
- Yamashiro, Jane. 2017. *Redefining Japaneseness: Japanese Americans in the Ancestral Homeland*. Rutgers University Press.
- Yan, Pearl. 2022. "Chef Sung Anh Takes A Leap Of Faith With Mosu Hong Kong." Michelin Guide. April 7. <https://guide.michelin.com/kr/en/article/people/chef-sung-anh-takes-a-leap-of-faith-with-mosu-hong-kong>.
- Yuh, Ji-Yeon. 2002. *Beyond the Shadow of Camptown: Korean Military Brides in America*. New York University Press.

Actually, Mother Really Didn't Like Jjajangmyeon

The Desire of Noodles in the Diaspora

ROBERT JI-SONG KU, UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, LOS ANGELES

If I had to name the single greatest debut song in the history of K-pop, I would choose “To Mother” by Groove Over Dose, a.k.a. g.o.d, first released in 1999.¹ Adding to the greatness is the music video, which features a very young Jang Hyuk, one of my favorite actors, in the leading role.² Several people were involved in writing and producing the song, including Park Jin-young (a.k.a. JY Park, a.k.a. The Asiansoul, a.k.a. JYP), who was instrumental in forming g.o.d under the EMB label founded by Teddy Hoon-tak Jung in 1997.³ Sometime later, g.o.d, who went on to dominate K-pop during the early 2000s, would retroactively list Tupac Shakur as one of the song’s composers since it was obvious that “To Mother” is a rearrangement of 2Pac’s “Life Goes On” (1996).⁴

1 By “greatest,” I mean groundbreaking tracks that kick-started phenomenal careers while simultaneously altering the future of music. Others I would place in this category include SES’s “I’m Your Girl” (1997), TVXQ’s “Hug” (2004), Big Bang’s “We Belong Together” (2006), Girls’ Generation’s “Into the New World” (2007), SHINee’s “Replay” (2008), IU’s “Lost Child” (2008), 2NE1’s “Fire” (2011), Exo’s “Mama” (2012), BTS’s “No More Dream” (2013), Red Velvet’s “Happiness” (2014), Twice’s “Like Ooh-Ahh” (2015), Seventeen’s “Adore U” (2015), Blackpink’s “Whistle” (2016), Stray Kids’s “District 9” (2018), IVE’s “Eleven” (2021), and New Jeans’s “Attention” (2022).

2 Coincidentally, Jang Hyuk stars in one of my favorite K-dramas of all time, *Thank You* (2007), whose storyline revolves around the struggles of a single mother, played by Gong Hyo-jin, and her HIV-positive daughter, played by the remarkable Seo Shin-ae, who was nine years old at the time.

3 EMB is now known as SidusHQ or iHQ.

4 It is perhaps not a coincidence that another idol group, Baby V.O.X—who, along with S.E.S. and Fin.K.L, represent the three most important first-generation girl idol groups—was also accused of not only illegally sampling Tupac’s music for their song “Xcstasy” in 2004, but also

“To Mother” chronicles the economic hardship of a single mother raising her teenage son in the face of poverty. At a pivotal point during the song’s narrative, the son complains to his mother that he is sick of eating instant *ramyeon* all the time, which prompts her to take money out of her emergency fund to buy him a bowl of *jjajangmyeon*. While happily eating, the son pauses to ask his mother why she is not eating with him. Her answer would become one of the most memorable lines in K-pop history: “Mother said that she didn’t like *jjajangmyeon*.”

The Best Bowl of Jjajangmyeon of My Life

Try as I might, I cannot think of another dish that speaks to my soul as much as *jjajangmyeon*. It is not that I think this is the most delicious dish in the world—far from it. If I had to pick my final “death row” meal, I do not think *jjajangmyeon* would even crack the top ten list. But, as we all know, the reason we yearn for and crave certain foods does not always hinge on how they taste but rather on the subjective and deeply personal meanings they convey.

First of all, what exactly is *jjajangmyeon*? For a quick answer, let us consult the old standby resource that we professor types often advise our students against using in their research papers, but we ourselves secretly cannot live without. *Jjajangmyeon*, according to Wikipedia,

is a Korean Chinese noodle dish topped with a thick sauce made of *chun-jang*, diced pork, and vegetables. It originated in Incheon, Korea where Chinese migrant workers brought over *zhajiangmian* from Shandong in the late 19th century. (Wikipedia 2024)

using his likeness in the music video. Unlike the men of g.o.d whose careers thrived despite the plagiarism controversy, the women of Baby V.O.X suffered the opposite fate. They ended up disbanding as a direct result when Lee Ha Neul, a member of the Korean hip-hop group DJ DOC, called them “sex singers.” Even greater damage was done to the group when Lee referred to them as “Miari V.O.X,” in reference to an infamous red-light district in Korea called Miari, which was near what is now Gireum Station in northern Seoul. This is despite the fact that while “To Mother” did, in fact, illegally sample Tupac, “Xcstasy” reportedly acquired all necessary legal permission to sample and use the likeness of Tupac in the song and the music video (Svetlana_M 2020).

I find this a surprisingly excellent definition, as good as any. But to better ruminate on and digest this definition, let us break it down into several bite-sized pieces.

First, jjajangmyeon “is a Korean Chinese dish.” While this descriptor sounds straightforward, it is impossible to ignore the inherent ambiguity: Does “Korean Chinese” suggest that the dish is part of Chinese cuisine made in a Korean style? Or does it imply that it is a dish affiliated with Chinese people who happen to be Korean, ethnically or otherwise? Given it could be either or both, would a simple word switch either resolve the ambiguity or, falling short of that, at least make the ambiguity itself less equivocal? That is to say, what if we described jjajangmyeon instead as a “Chinese Korean” dish, similar to the manner we commonly refer to chop suey or General Tso’s chicken as “Chinese American” dishes, to mean American fare made in a Chinese style or foods associated with Americans of Chinese descent? Whether it is more accurate to call jjajangmyeon “Korean Chinese” or “Chinese Korean,” one thing is certain: Chinese food exists on an unparalleled global scale and is dizzyingly complex and endlessly diverse.⁵

Second, jjajangmyeon “is a noodle dish.” While this bit of detail is sufficiently self-evident, it’s important to note that *jjajang* noodles are made of wheat flour and not, say, rice flour, buckwheat flour, sweet potato starch, acorn flour, or any other starch found in an array of Korean noodle dishes.⁶ In this regard, jjajangmyeon technically belongs to the category of *bunsik*, not the contemporary use of the term to mean inexpensive snack or street foods, such as *tteokbokki*, *ramyeon*, *sundae*, *kimbap*, *kalguksu*, or *twigim*, but the original, literal meaning of the word to mean food made from wheat flour.⁷ If asked to identify the single most significant factor that contributed to the dramatic transformation of Korean food after, say, the Korean War, I could reasonably point to the government’s 1963–76 pro-*bunsik* mandate, which came about in response to the postwar rice scarcity, and which essentially dictated how much rice an ordinary Korean

5 The diversity of Chinese cuisine on a global scale is a complex a subject as any in food studies. For a glimpse of its complexity, see Wu and Tan 2001, Moskin 2005, Tan 2011, and Wu and Cheung 2014.

6 The types of noodles common to Asian diets are virtually innumerable and many date back to ancient times (Fu 2008).

7 The social context and meanings related to street foods in Seoul have undergone numerous changes over the decades (Ku, Kim, and Yu 2021).

citizen was allowed to consume each week, and even when rice could be eaten, with rice proscribed for certain meals or on particular days. Intimately connected to the regulation of rice consumption during this period were the government propaganda and state policies regulating greater utilization of wheat products throughout the country.⁸

Third, the noodles are topped with a bunch of stuff, most notably *chunjang*, pork, and vegetables, usually onions and cabbage but also, at times, zucchini and potatoes. The key ingredient of jjajangmyeon is *chunjang* (or *tianmian* in Chinese), made of fermented wheat flour and soybeans (at a fixed 19:1 ratio), along with dark caramel. In this regard, *chunjang*, despite its Chinese origin, is now thoroughly Korean, as it comfortably sits alongside countless other fermented products that represent the backbone of Korean cookery—kimchi, *gochugang*, *doenjang*, *ssamjang*, *ganjang*, *jeot*, *sikcho*, and so forth. Among the most important culinary consequences of Korean food's reliance on fermented products is olfactory. As I have written elsewhere,

In other words, anything that makes Korean food *Korean* carries the potential of miasmic possibilities. . . . As food science has shown, the natural outcome of the process of fermentation—or bacterially produced lactic acid fermentation, to be more specific—is tanginess of flavor and smell. To say that Korean food tastes and smells tangy would be the gastronomic understatement of the century. (Ku 2018)

Fourth, jjajangmyeon “originated in Incheon.” This is where I enter the picture since I also originated in the city of Incheon; it is my birthplace and was my home until I was eight years old, when my family emigrated to Hawai‘i in the early 1970s. But it was some 120 years before my birth that Incheon was first established as a city upon becoming a trade port with China in 1883 (Lee and Lou 2019). Legend has it that the first restaurant that sold jjajangmyeon to the public was a Chinese establishment called Gonghwachun (originally named Shangdong Huiguan), which just happens to be the current location of the Jjajangmyeon Museum, first established in 2012, in the heart of Incheon’s Chinatown.

8 To better understand the political motivations behind the pro-bunsik initiative that discouraged rice consumption while encouraging wheat consumption, see Cwierka 2012, 114–41; Yoo 2017, 107–18; and Kim 2019, 130–14.

Finally, it was “Chinese migrant workers” who “brought over zhajiangmian from Shandong in the late 19th century.” In this regard, zhajiangmian is the direct progenitor of Korean jjajangmyeon. Chinese zhajiangmian is commonly referred to as Beijing Fried Sauce Noodles, one of “China’s Top 10 Famous Noodles” as determined by the Ministry of Commerce and China Hotel Association (Shi 2013). The list also includes the famous Shanxi knife-cut noodles, Lanzhou hand-pulled noodles, and Sichuan *dandanmian* (Shi 2013). *Zhajiang* (or *jjajang*) means “fried,” which is an essential step in making the dish since *chunjang* is literally fried in oil during the cooking process.

My earliest memory of eating at a sit-down restaurant goes back to when I was around five or six. It just happened to be at a Chinese Korean restaurant in Incheon sometime in the late 1960s, when Korea was among the poorest places in the world, and decades before it somehow miraculously became one of the top ten global economies. Although I have only vague memories of my childhood in Korea, for some reason I am certain that it was my *samchon* (my mother’s youngest brother), dressed in a high school uniform with his head shaved, who treated me to my first-ever bowl of jjajangmyeon. And if my memory serves me right, it was the most delicious thing I had ever tasted in my life up to that point. Since that moment, I have been on a lifelong quest to find a bowl of jjajangmyeon that is equally delicious. So far, more than a half-century later, this quest remains unfulfilled.

The Chinese Korean (*Hwagyo*) Diaspora

Until I left for college to California, dinner at home usually meant Korean food. In addition to working as a hotel maid in Waikiki during the day and as a cook and dishwasher at night, my mother also had to look after her three children and my father, who worked the red-eye shift at a local strip club as a bartender, a vocation he picked up while working at an American military base back in Korea. This meant that my overworked mother prepared food that was principally meant to fill the family’s stomachs, not delight our taste buds. It also had to be cheap, fast, and simple to rustle up. If the food turned out to be tasty, well, that was a bonus.

One such item that fulfilled all these conditions for me—filling, cheap, simple, fast, and tasty—was Sapporo Ichiban Ramen, which at the

time was among the most popular brands of instant ramen in Hawai'i, and, I suspect, the world. Among everything my mother cooked, this was hands-down my favorite meal, especially when she spiced it up with gochujang or gochugaru and added a soft-poached egg. It was not until years later that I realized the deeper meaning of instant ramen, which, according to a Fuji Research Institute survey conducted in 2000, was voted by the Japanese public as the greatest Japanese invention of the twentieth century. It easily beat out karaoke machines, which came in second, and the Sony Walkman, which came in at number three (ABC News 2000). And I had no idea at the time that the instant ramen my mother cooked for me was not Korean but rather Japanese—and, if we go back far enough, Chinese.

During Korea's rise up the economic ladder, and especially over the past two decades, the country has become increasingly more international and multicultural. Tourism from overseas has surged, particularly from China. In 2016 alone, some seven million Chinese tourists, representing half of all foreign tourists, visited the country. Korea's attitude toward the rise of Chinese tourism has been ambivalent at best. While Koreans welcome the economic windfall that accompanies Chinese tourism, they at the same time resent the proliferation of Chinese people in their midst and essentially scapegoat them for a whole host of domestic problems, including the horrendous air pollution, such as the yellow dust that frequently descends upon all of Korea (Bicker 2019; Lee 2019). Of course, Korea is not the only country in the world to have scapegoated the Chinese. The United States, for instance, has had a long history of blaming the country's economic and social ills on ethnic and racial "others." In fact, one might say that scapegoating the Chinese is as American as baseball, Chevrolet, and chop suey.⁹

And this is not new to Korea either. In fact, this ambivalence toward the presence of Chinese people on Korean soil dates back to the late nineteenth century, when approximately four thousand Chinese soldiers and merchants established a post in Incheon following the Military Mutiny of 1882. To wit, in 1922, during the height of the Japanese colonial period, the *Hwagyo* (the Chinese community that had settled in Korea), who

9 The discrimination against and exclusion of Chinese people in U.S. history is among the most researched subject matters in Asian American studies. To begin, see Chan 1991, Lee 2003, and Kurashige 2016.

represented a mere 0.5 percent of the total Korean population, accounted for 6.52 percent of all business taxes collected. In 1931, the Hwagyo were subjected to mob violence, with approximately 150 Chinese killed during riots and lynchings at the hands of angry Koreans. The scapegoating of the Hwagyo continued after the war, as Koreans continued to regard them as economic, political, and cultural threats. The Park Chung-hee military rule of the 1960s and 70s, for instance, established economic policies to specifically curb Chinese business activities and limit their land ownership (Kwon 2021; Yang 2005).

This historic intolerance compelled the majority of ethnic Chinese Koreans, even those whose families have lived in Korea since the early 1900s in places such as Incheon's Chinatown, to emigrate to Taiwan, Canada, and other places, including the United States, to form the Chinese Korean diaspora, prompting the *New York Times* in 2007 to call the Incheon neighborhood a Chinatown that “lacks only one thing—Chinese people” (Onishi 2001). After settling elsewhere around the world, displaced Chinese Koreans established livelihoods that often involved one of the few occupations made available to them—running Chinese restaurants largely for the benefit of Korean diasporic communities, such as the one in Hawai'i, a community for which a bowl of jjajangmyeon meant being able to maintain a sense of Koreanness via the power of gastronomic nostalgia.

Unlike the Jang Hyuk character in g.o.d's “To Mother” music video, I never tired of eating instant ramen. However, like him, what brought me the greatest joy was when my father would take me to eat jjajangmyeon at the Eastern Paradise Chinese Restaurant on Ke'eaumoku Street near the Ala Moana Shopping Center in Honolulu. If any bowl of jjajangmyeon came close to being as delicious as the first bowl my samchon treated me to back in Incheon, this was it. But rather than the food, what I remember most distinctly about Eastern Paradise are the women who worked there. To most customers, who were Koreans like my father and me, the waitresses and cashiers spoke fluent Korean. To non-Koreans, they spoke in English—or Hawaiian Pidgin, rather. But among themselves, they spoke in what, at the time to me, sounded like Chinese. I do not think I ever got around to asking my father about this linguistic mystery, which I did not solve until many years later.

Coda

If anyone should love jjajangmyeon, it is my mother, who was born in Incheon, just a stone's throw from Chinatown, and lived there all her life until she moved with her family to Hawai'i. This is where she met my father, a refugee from the north, whose family migrated south during the war in stereotypical fashion, carrying bundles on their heads and desperately hanging onto crowded railroad cars teeming with other desperate refugees fleeing the communists in the north.

What this meant was that I was confronted with a binary dilemma from early on in my life: Am I team jjajangmyeon, since I was also born in Incheon, or am I team *naengmyeon*, which was my father's favorite dish, bar none. The answer, at least before I entered adulthood, was easy: jjajangmyeon was always a source of joy, while a bowl of naengmyeon was an ordeal to consume. While the worst outcome from jjajangmyeon might be a shirt splattered with dots of jjajang sauce (which I did not mind one bit), eating a bowl of naengmyeon meant gagging on the elastic noodles that were impossible for me to chew or bite through with my gap-filled boyhood teeth.

As long as I can remember, my mother never liked jjajangmyeon. It is safe to say that she rather hated it, so much so that a Chinese Korean restaurant was the last place she wanted to eat, if given the choice. If she ended up there, mostly to acquiesce to my father's unpredictable moods, she never ordered jjajangmyeon. Neither did she opt for *jjamppong*, which, of course, is the other half of the all-important binary choice all Koreans have to make when eating at a Chinese Korean establishment: Are you team jjajangmyeon or team jjamppong? For my mother, it was neither. And the reason she cited always remained the same: She hated bunsik, not the contemporary use of the term to mean, say, inexpensive street or pojang food, but the word's original, literal meaning of food made from wheat flour. I am sick of it, she would say. She was sick of it because food made with wheat flour, such as *sujebi* and *kalguksu*, reminded her too much of being hungry back in Korea.

In this regard, unlike the story told in g.o.d's "To Mother," where jjajangmyeon represents luxury, to my mother, the noodle dish has always reminded her of the poverty-stricken years of her youth. So yes, actually,

my mother genuinely did not like jjajangmyeon—and still does not, some fifty-plus years after leaving her birthplace, Incheon.

References

- ABC News. 2000. "Japanese Name Noodles Best Invention." December 12. <https://abcnews.go.com/International/story?id=81946&page=1>.
- Bicker, Laura. 2019. "South Korea Pollution: Is China the Cause of 'Fine Dust'?" BBC News. June 6. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-48346344>.
- Chan Sucheng, ed. 1991. *Entry Denied: Exclusion and the Chinese Community in America, 1882–1943*. Temple University Press.
- Fu, Bin Xiao. 2008. "Asian Noodles: History, Classification, Raw Materials, and Processing." *Food Research International* 41 (2008): 888–902.
- Ku, Robert Ji-Song, Jungah Kim, and Hyunjoo Yu. 2021. "Beyond Pojangmacha: Edae Food Carts and the Future of Seoul's Social Gastronomy." *Food, Culture & Society* 24 (1): 84–97.
- Ku, Robert Ji-Song. 2018. "'Is that Kimchi in My Taco?' A Vision of Korean American Food in One Bite." In *A Companion to Korean American Studies*, edited by Rachael Miyung Joo and Shelley Sang-Hee Lee. Brill.
- Kurashige, Lon. 2016. *The Two Faces of Exclusion: The Untold History of Anti-Asian Racism in the United States*. University of North Carolina Press.
- Kwon, Oh-Jung. 2021. "Constructing Chineseness as Other in the Evolution of National Identity in South Korea." *Identities* 28 (4): 454–71.
- Lee, David D. 2019. "China Is to Blame for South Korea's Air Pollution. Really?" *South China Morning Post*, March 15. <https://www.scmp.com/week-asia/health-environment/article/3001741/china-blame-south-koreas-air-pollution-really>.
- Lee, Erica. 2003. *At America's Gates: Chinese Immigration during the Exclusion Era, 1882–1943*. University of North Carolina Press.
- Lee, Jerry Won, and Jackie Jia Lou. 2019. "The Ordinary Semiotic Landscape of an Unordinary Place: Spatiotemporal Disjunctures in Incheon's Chinatown." *International Journal of Multilingualism* 16 (2): 187.
- Moskin, Julia. 2005. "Craving Hyphenated Chinese." *New York Times*. September 21.
- Onishi, Norimitsu. 2001. "This Chinatown Lacks Only One Thing—Chinese." *New York Times*. March 1.
- Shi Liwei. 2013. "Top 10 Chinese Noodles." ChinaCulture.org. July 22. https://en.chinaculture.org/focus/2013-07/22/content_472703.htm.
- Svetlana_M. 2020. "Did New Kpop Fans ever hear of BABY VOX?" allkpop. January 10. <https://www.allkpop.com/article/2020/01/did-new-kpop-fans-ever-hear-of-baby-vox>.

- Tan, Chee-Beng, ed. 2011. *Chinese Food and Foodways in Southeast Asia and Beyond*. NUS Press.
- Wikipedia. 2024. "Jajangmyeon." Last modified July 19. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jajangmyeon>.
- Wu, David Y. H., and Sidney C. H. Cheung, eds. 2014. *The Globalization of Chinese Food*. Routledge.
- Wu, David Y. H., and Chee-Beng Tan, eds. 2001. *Changing Chinese Foodways in Asia*. Chinese University Press
- Yang, Young-Kyun. 2005. "Jajangmyeon and Junggukjip: The Changing Position and Meaning of Chinese Food and Chinese Restaurants in Korean Society." *Korea Journal* 45 (2): 60–88.

The Stickiness of Zainichi Korean Food Routes

Food Memoir as Affective Archive

JOOYEON RHEE, PENN STATE UNIVERSITY

Born and raised on Cheju Island, Kim Yangnŭng was about fifteen when she boarded the *Kimigayo Maru* in the mid-1930s, a Japanese steamship that transported people and goods between Osaka and Cheju Island (see figure 1). Yangnŭng first worked in a spinning mill in Wakayama, a city near Osaka, and then settled in the Ikaino district shortly after marrying a man also from Cheju. This man, Hong Yea, had first gone to Manchuria, where many Koreans had migrated to become farmers, merchants, independence fighters, and bandits (*majök*¹); Yea was a bandit. Ikaino, where Korean migrant workers had formed a close-knit community since the early 1910s, no longer exists on maps of Osaka, as it was annexed to nearby districts in the early 1970s. However, the district still stands strong in the minds of Koreans living in Japan, as does the Ikuno district, where present-day Koreatown is located.

Yangnŭng had a stall and sold rice cakes at the Ikaino market; her rice cake recipes were famous among the Koreans who shopped there. Called “Rice Cake Grandma,” she handed down her recipes and business to her daughter-in-law, Kang Chaesun, also from Cheju and one of those fortu-

1 Some Koreans were indeed involved in criminal activities as bandits or drug traffickers. However, it must be also noted that the term “majök,” used commonly by newspapers and the colonial state at the time, referred a category broader than “bandit”—it also referred to Korean and Chinese anti-Japanese guerilla fighters.

nate enough to escape the 4.3 Massacre of 1948.² The resulting Tokuyama Products business group—founded by Kim Yangnŭng, then continued by her daughter-in-law, grandchildren, and great-grandchildren—is revered by virtually everyone in Ikaino for its long business history and its active engagement in *Zainichi* community-building (see figure 2).³

FIGURE I. The Second Kimigayo Maru (used by permission from the Osaka Koreatown History Museum)

2 The 1948–49 uprising on Cheju (Jeju) Island and the subsequent violent crackdown under President Syngman Rhee resulted in the mass killing of an enormous number of civilians, with lower estimates ranging from at least 14,000 to as high as 30,000. The beginning of the uprising is traditionally regarded as April 3 (thus, “4.3”), 1948. Discussion of the massacre was quashed under Rhee and the next two military regimes; in 1998, Kim Daejung finally publically recognized the massacre.

3 The literal meaning of *Zainichi* is “being in Japan,” and it generally refers to Koreans living in Japan. However, depending on a person’s nationality (*kokuseki*) or non-nationality (*mukokuseki*), and their preference beyond nationality, they are referred to and refer to themselves using terms such as *Zainichi Kankokujin* (Koreans living in Japan with South Korean nationality), *Zainichi Chōsenjin* (Koreans living in Japan with North Korean nationality) and *mukokusekisha* (person with no nationality).

FIGURE 2. Tokuyama Group Building (author's photo, May 2023)

This essay focuses on *Way of Painting, Way of Food* (2019), a memoir or biography⁴ by Hong Söngik (1956–), Kim’s eldest grandson. As sketched above, his grandparents moved to Japan during colonial times, seeking employment, while his parents are survivors of the 4.3 Massacre who fled to Japan and lived first as stateless people, then as North Korean citizens, and finally, as South Korean citizens in Japan, a meandering route that was quite common among Koreans living in Ikaino. Hong’s border-crossing experiences have been as intricate as those of his grandparents and parents, moving across Japan and both Koreas but also moving along and around the rules, restrictions, and borders marking

4 Hong expressed that he desired to leave a “memoir” about his life as a painter and a businessman, but he asked a journalist to interview him and write it. It is unclear how this book should be categorized without knowing how the division of labor was carried out.

the inter-imperial temporalities and geographies of Cold War East Asia. Tracing his seemingly impossible double pursuit of art and food both simultaneously and successively in the last five decades, Hong's account of his life and that of his family lays bare the historical realities that not only have limited the mobility of Koreans living in Japan, but also engendered emotional tensions, ideological conflicts, and psychological and geographic divisions among that community.

Hong writes about his family's history of displacement, border-crossing, and trauma in *Way of Painting, Way of Food*, interweaving his reflections on and practice of art with his experiences running food businesses in Japan, South Korea, and North Korea. Hong is meticulous about informing his readers of historical facts and his family's history, illustrating his account with family photos and his paintings, making the memoir a valuable archive. To circumvent the common perception of the memoir as a biased or dubious genre of writing, he had the established journalist, Kawase Shunji, interview him for about a year and then write the memoir.⁵ However, another compelling aspect of the memoir is the unusual mix of high art with the seemingly mechanical nature of food-making, which remaps the boundary of the genre, making it highly elusive and elastic. This elusive/elastic quality is generative in a few ways. First, it provides a constructive way to engage with the intricacy and everydayness of the inter-regional and intergenerational imagination of border crossing, which is not easily grasped by using established political theories or examining diplomatic policies. Sociologist Krishnendu Ray's critique of the cultural hierarchy associated with cooking resonates with the way Hong deals with art and food together in his writing. Ray explains how his own experience of cooking and tasting showed him

how the terms of exchange between domains of cultural activity, art, and everyday cooking can shift dramatically with displacement and re-emplacement—that is, migration, in my case—a fact unaccounted

5 I am indebted to a Zainichi Korean living in Osaka, "K," who helped me communicate with Hong. K delivered Hong's reasons why he collaborated with Kawase Shunji. First, Hong did not think he had the ability to write well and wanted to have a qualified writer for the book. Second, Kawase showed a deep interest in food for a long time, persuading Hong to write a book on food together. Third, Hong's original plan for the book was to remain objective about historical facts and add extensive fieldwork. However, before Hong and Kawase carried out this plan, Hong was diagnosed with cancer. With the future uncertain, Hong changed the overall direction of the book, instead interweaving his life stories, Zainichi food culture, and his art.

for in Bourdieu's analysis of taste and hierarchy. Transplantation can sharpen perception and cognition by redeploying old concepts in new contexts. (2016, xvi)

Hong's memoir is a text that makes a critical intervention into hegemonic aestheticism by addressing the material and intellectual dissonance between established discourse and unrecognized everyday practice by mixing his account of high artistry with his enmeshment in the "low culture" of the food business.

Second, it uses food as a medium to delineate multiple layers of intimacy between the material and intellectual realms of diasporic life. His portrayals of the people appearing in his memoir, as well as the relations he creates between the readers and the text, are not always positive or optimistic, but frequently convey feelings of betrayal, misunderstanding, and the unpredictability of everyday life itself. Lauren Berlant (1998, 282) problematizes the ubiquitous privileging of "utopian, optimism-sustaining versions of intimacy" that fail to address the ambivalence of the private and intimate spheres. The mediation of intimacy by cultural hegemonies built on normative notions like "nation" or "love," she argues, neglects the "unavoidable troubles, the distractions and disruptions that make things turn out in unpredicted scenarios" (281). As this paper will show, the stickiness of Hong's memoir calls to mind Berlant's emphasis on the daily experience of intimacy that is inevitably ambivalent, contradictory, unstable, unpredictable, and constantly on the move. More specifically, Hong evokes the affective power of autobiography by underlining how border-crossing is a sticky matter for Zainichi Koreans, as the complexity of geopolitics has divided communities and families and made crossing borders extremely challenging even in the post-Cold War era. By looking at *Way of Painting*, *Way of Food* as a vernacular history and an affective archive, this essay argues that the memoir, both as an aesthetic form and as a political act, enables us to apprehend the embodied experience of migration and that food is an integral part of this embodiment.

Zainichi Food Practices and the Minor Kitchen

Zainichi communities in Japan witnessed a surprising rise in the popularity of Korean food starting in the early 2000s, which mainly stemmed from the so-called Korean Wave (*hallyu*) of the mainstream popularity of

everything Korean. But even before the arrival of hallyu, some Korean dishes were already widely consumed, notably kimchi (pickled cabbage) and *yakiniku* (Korean-style barbecue). Recent studies show that kimchi has become one of the most popular dishes in Japan, while yakiniku is more popular there than finely marbled domestic beef (Demelius 2023; Miyatsuka 1999) since the 1990s. It must be noted that the study of Korean food in the Japanese context generally neglects how these dishes have been sourced and consumed. In addition, although hallyu has made South Korean culture highly visible in Japan, scholarly interest in the Japanese consumption of Korean food rarely covers the everydayness of Zainichi Korean culinary practices. Some recent food scholarship, though, has addressed this in noteworthy ways, attending to previously marginalized topics like gendered food practices in Zainichi communities. Yoko Demelius (2023), for example, shows how Korean women's engagement with the Japanese public through the making and sharing of kimchi functions as a diplomatic tool to help make Zainichi Korean existence more visible in Japan. More importantly, Demelius focuses on a very important space often dismissed in Zainichi studies: the kitchen. Kitchens are generally considered women's spaces across societies and cultures, and migrant kitchens are no exception. Women in kitchens invest their physical labor, culinary skills, and care for family and the community into their work, but this investment rarely garners scholarly or any other recognition. Those in charge of migrant kitchens often invest extra care and time to attain resources common in their home country—such as ingredients and tools—that are hard to come by in their newly adopted country. In this regard, Zainichi Korean women, making and sharing kimchi with the Japanese members of their communities, exemplify the power of women's work as it moves beyond the migrant kitchen and transforms domestic and private labor into public and political activity. As Jackie Kim-Wachutak argues (2023, 4), Zainichi women have been “continuously challenging the oppressive and discriminatory structural powers” in Japan by showing the importance of paying attention to women's everyday lives as a way to locate their subjectivity.

I use the term “the minor kitchen” to refer to Zainichi Korean food practices, but I do not mean to limit these practices to those performed by women or highlight only the marginality of the migrant kitchen; rather, the minor kitchen is both a material and symbolic repository of

the minoritarian power to challenge both structural and discursive discrimination against Zainichi Koreans in both Japan and North and South Korea.⁶ Hong's memoir uses the minor kitchen to articulate the complex positionality of Zainichi Koreans, showing how this makes them vulnerable in all three countries (Japan, South Korea, and North Korea), while also critiquing the hegemonic forces responsible for this vulnerability.

Hong opens his memoir with his family's experiences during the April 3 Cheju Uprising and Massacre, while also positioning Cheju as the origin of the "taste" that the Tokuyama Group was created to reproduce. Hong's grandmother and mother used recipes handed down from his great aunt, a Buddhist nun in Cheju in colonial times. This great aunt's kitchen, located in a small Buddhist temple, was famous throughout Cheju, especially the rice cakes produced there. Her experience of the massacre is one of the many stories of horror and madness experienced by people in Cheju, especially her encounters with Christian groups that constantly threatened to destroy her temple. To others, such as Hong's parents, the deaths of relatives and friends left deep trauma that was difficult to talk about, not just due to the intensity of the trauma but also due to their fears that the South Korean government would retaliate if they exposed state violence. Hong's father passed away without ever articulating his experience, and it was only seventy years later that Hong's mother mustered the courage to tell Hong about her own experience.

It was in 1948 that the Hong family established the Tokuyama Group in Osaka, in an area that would go on to host the largest community of Korean people in postwar Japan, including a massive number of people who escaped the massacre in Cheju in much the same way his mother and father did.⁷ At a time when Koreans in Japan found it hard to survive due to a lack of employment and even food, one may wonder how a rice cake business could support itself. The business's survival, though, shows us how Zainichi Koreans religiously kept their traditions even during hardship, particularly the annual and seasonal ancestral rituals that required rice cakes for their ritual tables. Although Hong does not

6 Tens of thousands of Zainichi Koreans were repatriated to both North and South Korea.

7 It took several failed attempts before Hong's mother reached Osaka from Cheju to unite with her mother. Hong's father stayed temporarily in Cheju, sent by his grandfather shortly after postwar liberation, but he ended up forced to escape South Korea back to Japan, a process that involved Hong's great aunt hiding him in her temple before sending him on to Osaka.

mention them explicitly, the frequent shamanistic rituals performed in the community, especially among people from Cheju, also played an important role in sustaining the business.

Hong's father was deeply engaged in political activities while running the rice cake factory, promoting the rights of Korean people in Japan via his affiliation with the *Chongryon* (General Association of Korean Residents). Hong thus was educated up to college in *Chosŏn* schools founded by the Chongryon community, studying art in hopes of becoming a painter. His primary professional interest was art, and this passion led him to South Korea, where he continued producing paintings throughout the late 1980s. He worked to maintain a veneer of political neutrality during this time, even as he witnessed Zainichi Koreans often being scapegoated because of the South Korean state's anti-communist stance.⁸ At the same time, his affiliation with Chongryon led him to make contacts with leftist activists and politicians in South Korea, who, much to his disappointment, regarded him primarily as a tool to advance their political goals. Hong, hoping to re-root in South Korea and contribute to the South Korean food industry by setting up rice cake and noodle factories, even changed his nationality from North Korean to South Korean. This decision motivated his parents to switch their national affiliations as well, resulting in them becoming targets of harassment from the Chongryon community, as they were seen as betraying the "home country"—that is, North Korea.

Starting in the late 1980s, thanks to the democratization of South Korea, Hong began to enjoy greater mobility compared to the first and second generations of Koreans in Japan. He was the first person to establish an *okononiyaki* restaurant in South Korea, was responsible for transferring technologies necessary for rice cake production to Korean businesses like CJ Foods, and took part in a long series of negotiations with North Korea to build a factory for producing the noodles used in *naengmyon*. It was not Hong's passion and dedication alone that enabled him to cross these borders; geographical proximity, the shared culinary practices between Japan and the Koreans, and the well-established commerce and trade partnership between Japan and South Korea must also factor in. The Lotte Group, along with Moranbong Food, are perhaps the most successful cases of Zainichi Koreans "re-rooting" through business.

8 The South Korean government viewed Zainichi as communist sympathizers, sometimes branding them as North Korean spies; some were jailed and even sentenced to death.

While much smaller than Lotte, Moranbong Food is well-established in Japan. It also has a Korean branch that sells Korean and Japanese products, mostly condiments.

One thing that makes Hong's food route unusual is his desire to embrace both Koreas. This has caused strain and difficulty for him due to the ideological divisions within the Zainichi Korean community and their precarity in relation to both states. Hong focuses on consumption trends, business models and opportunities, real and imagined borders, and everyday interactions with other Koreans without resorting to nostalgia for or romanticization of his ancestral home. At the same time, he does not deny the pleasure of seeing his Korean food products bought and sold by people in both countries, aligning this with the pleasure he experiences when people come to see his paintings at exhibitions in both South Korea and Japan.

Food and Art, Food as Art

It is an open secret that Hong was the primary force behind the recently founded Osaka Koreatown History Museum. Located in the heart of Koreatown, it was established by elected community members to promote awareness of the history of Koreans in Japan. The memorial stone by the museum's gate displays an engraving that reads *kyōsei no hi* (literally, "a memorial stone of symbiotic way of life"), emphasizing the importance of Korean and Japanese co-existence. The museum houses various archives—books, photographs, films, video recordings, maps, etc.—that are exhibited regularly. Symbiosis represents Hong's philosophy of art as well. The theme of one of his series of paintings was "prayer," and was meant to portray Zainichi Koreans' wish to return to a united homeland. His real-life experiences in South Korea made him revise this theme, as he realized that the dream of returning to a homeland was not only unrealistic but also one far removed from the everyday struggles of the Zainichi people. Their struggle was to find a way to "live" with others, he states, and this is the essence of the diasporic life he both witnessed and personally experienced. Hong's company motto is "Food is Art" (189), reflecting his emphasis that both are forms of "nourishment" that feed others.

The Hong family's contribution to community-building that embraces all people in Osaka, regardless of ethnicity, can also be seen in the *Pan'ga sikkongbang* (Pan'ga Korean food studio), founded in 2003. The studio was first used primarily by children, who were provided with food to accompany educational programs about the history of Koreans in Japan. Its purview gradually expanded into a contact zone where Japanese people of all ages could come and learn about Korean food-making. The studio also exhibits various kinds of art, thus becoming a contact zone for experiencing Korean and Japanese art. In this way, the studio can be seen as an ethnographic and artistic encounter with the entanglements of Zainichi Korean history, poetically interwoven with visual and sensorial aesthetics. Ben Highmore (2013) once called such attentiveness to meaning-making via everyday acts like cooking as “gastro-poetics.”

FIGURE 3. Osaka Koreatown History Museum (author's photo, May 2023)

By characterizing our initial contact with the world as aesthetic, aesthetics is both foundational and preliminary. It is neither the epiphenomena scaffolded onto something of more basic significance nor the final word on our apprehension of, and agency in, the world. This dual status as a sort of provisional foundation makes it such a significant

arena for cultural studies' involvement. An artwork is not meant to serve as representative of a particular kind of experience. In the world of aesthetics, it is the singularity of experience that counts, but singularity is not the refusal of the social; rather, it is the social refined yet unfinished. To move from the singular to the social does not require the generalization of experience but the detailing of its specific grammar—its poetics—as the figural forms connect to an alimentary geography and a set of possible feelings (Highmore 2013, 101).

Hong describes the embodied experience of the everyday labor involved in food production, juxtaposing the process of art-making with the process of rice cake-making in the last part of his memoir. His detailed description of making rice cakes evokes the sensory aspects of the process of transforming rice into powder and then into cakes. The description of steaming the rice cakes and the ways his parents and workers engage in this labor seems intended to show how the story of the Tokuyama Group is more than the story of handling materials and machinery; it is instead one that traces the entangled movement of bodies, culinary knowledge, and lifeways across the sticky borders of history.

References

- Berlant, Lauren. 1998. "Intimacy: A Special Issue." *Critical Inquiry* 24 (2): 281–88.
- Demelius, Yoko. 2023. "The Presentation of the Korean Self with Everyday Food: Negotiating 'Koreanness' through Kimchi Diplomacy in Contemporary Japan." *Seoul Journal of Korean Studies* 36 (1): 87–116.
- Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari. 1986. *Kafka: Toward a Minor Literature*, translated by Dana B. Polan. University of Minnesota Press.
- Highmore, Ben. 2013. "Migrant Cuisine, Critical Regionalism and Gastro-poetics." *Cultural Studies Review* 19 (1):99–116.
- Hong Söngik. 2019. *Doya, doya, doya: e no michi, shoku no michi fun'tōki* [How's that, how's that, how's that: my fight for the way of painting and the way of food]. Tōhō shuppan.
- Kim-Wachutka, Jackie J. 2023. "Zainichi Korean Women and Intersectional Visibility: Private Talk, Public Speech, Political Act—Seeking Justice in Japan." *Seoul Journal of Korean Studies* 36 (1): 167–201.
- Miyatsuka, Toshio. 1999. "Yakiniku: Savory Dishes with Simple Origins." *Japan Quarterly* 46 (4): 31–41.
- Mizuno Naoki, and Mun Gyeongsu. 2015. *Zainichi Chōsenjin: Rekishi to gen-zai* [Zainichi Koreans: History and today]. Iwanami shoten.
- Ray, Krishnendu. 2016. *The Ethnic Restaurateur*. Bloomsbury.

Shorenstein APARC director Gi-Wook Shin (left) with conference participants Robert Ji-Song Ku, Jooyeon Rhee, Soh Kim, Ryu Soo-young, Chef Judy Joo, Dafna Zur, and Rebecca Jo Kinney (photo by Rod Searcey).

Stanford

Walter H. Shorenstein
Asia-Pacific Research Center
Freeman Spogli Institute